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**THE PERIOD OF EMERGENCE AND FORMATION OF THE PIPE
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Abstract: This article provides information about the emergence and formation period of the trumpet musical instrument. Also, the theoretical importance and features of the trumpet instrument in musical culture are highlighted.

Key words: Music culture, trumpet, musical instruments, art, musical work.

Trumpet (Old Upper trumba; Italian tromba, French trompette, German Trompete, English trumpet) is a brass wind musical instrument of the alto-soprano register, the highest in sound among brass wind instruments. Since ancient times, the natural trumpet has been used as a signal instrument, and from about the 17th century it became part of the orchestra. With the invention of the valve mechanism, the trumpet received a full chromatic scale and from the middle of the 19th century became a full-fledged instrument of classical music. It has a bright, brilliant timbre and is used as a solo instrument or in symphony and brass bands, as well as in jazz and other genres. The trumpet is used in various musical traditions, including Russian.

The one who plays the trumpet is called the trumpeter. In the guards and the army of the Russian Empire (cavalry and artillery), there was a lower rank "Trumpeter", it was a soldier who gave signals. A similar function in the infantry was performed by a bugler (from the word horn). The trumpet is one of the oldest musical instruments. Mentions of the oldest instruments of this type date back to about 3600 BC. [6] Pipes existed in many civilizations - in Ancient Egypt, Ancient Greece, Ancient China, etc., and were used as signal instruments. The trumpet played this role for many centuries, until the 17th century. In antiquity, there was a technology for making tools from one single sheet of metal.

In the Middle Ages, trumpeters were obligatory members of the army, only they could quickly convey the order of the commander to other parts of the army that were at a distance with the help of a signal. The art of playing the trumpet was considered "elite", it was taught only to specially selected people. In peacetime, trumpets sounded at festive processions, knightly tournaments, in large cities there was a position of "tower" trumpeters who announced the arrival of a high-ranking person, a change in the time of day (thus acting as a kind of clock), the approach of enemy troops to the city and other events .

At the turn of the Middle Ages and the Renaissance, thanks to the improvement of pipe manufacturing technology, interest in these tools increased significantly. During the Baroque era, composers begin to incorporate trumpet parts into the orchestra. There are virtuoso performers who possessed the art of "clarino" (performing a diatonic scale in the upper register of the pipe with the help of blowing). The Baroque period can rightfully be called the "golden age of the natural pipe". With the advent of classicism and romanticism, the fundamental principle of which was melody, natural pipes, unable to perform melodic lines, fade into the background and are used in orchestras only to perform the main steps of the scale.

The valve mechanism, invented in the 1830s and giving the trumpet a chromatic scale, was not widely used at first, since not all chromatic sounds were pure intonation and identical in timbre. Since that time, the top voice in the brass group has increasingly been entrusted to the cornet, an instrument related to the pipe with a softer timbre and more advanced technical capabilities. Cornets (along with trumpets) were the orchestra's permanent instruments until the early 20th century, when improvements in instrument design and trumpeters' skill almost eliminated the problem of fluency and timbre, and cornets disappeared from the orchestra. In our time, the orchestral parts of the cornets are usually performed on the pipes, although the original instrument is sometimes used.

The natural, or ancient, trumpet is historically the first variety of the musical trumpet itself—that is, it was used not for practical, but for aesthetic purposes. Its distinguishing features are a predominantly cylindrical section, which turns into a conical one rather late, as well as a relatively small bell and mouthpiece. In total, the pipe of this kind was very long (about twice as long as the modern chromatic pipe) and belonged to the number of instruments with a narrow scale, which made it possible to reproduce a wide range of sounds with it without much effort - in principle, if desired, by combining different tunings on it was possible to obtain an almost complete chromatic scale.

However, the composers of the classical period did not use the full range of its possibilities, since during this period the pipes, as well as percussion instruments, were used occasionally and sporadically in orchestras, often to reproduce some individual sounds or simple melodic turns. Due to the impossibility of using closed sounds, the trumpet parts of that time were less rich than, for example, the horn parts, but this was partly compensated by the specifics of their sound itself. Notes for the natural trumpet, as well as for the

French horn, were written in the key "sol"; due to its design features, the performer could not change the original pitch of the sounds, so the composers had to focus only on the sounds naturally produced by the instrument's tube itself.

The sound in the old trumpet was extracted freely and with a high degree of accuracy, so even with the use of a rather limited set of auxiliary techniques, it could be played quite quickly. During the period of the clarino style, or, as it is called alternatively, during the time of the polyphonists, the technique of playing the natural trumpet received a certain development, but subsequently the performing style again returned mainly to the reproduction of simple melodic constructions or simple harmonies. The classical orchestra at that time used, as a rule, two pipes in combination with timpani and horns, but there were also more numerous variations - depending on the specifics of specific works. In later periods, as the strength of the orchestra increased, the number of pipes also increased: for example, R. Wagner in the "March of the Knights" from the opera "Tannhäuser" used 12 pipes at once.

As soon as the musicians realized the fundamental limitations of the natural pipe, various attempts were made to improve it and apply new design solutions. The varieties of pipes obtained as a result of these searches had a purely temporary significance in the history of orchestral performance, but they played a role in the development of the instrument and its current appearance. Generalization and systematization of the range of proposed options allow us to say that a total of three attempts were made with varying degrees of success.

The first attempt, which dates back to about the 18th century, was the intention to apply the technique of "closed sounds" to the pipe. This technique had been developed some time before and was used on the French horn; the performer put his hand into the bell of the instrument, thereby achieving a different sound. To provide the player with the opportunity to perform such an action, a natural semi-oval pipe was designed, resembling a crescent moon in appearance (in connection with which, in France, for example, it received the corresponding name - French trompette demi-lune). The crown "fa" was the main one for her, there was also the possibility to translate the scale into "e-flat" or "re". The bell, respectively, was directed sideways during the game. While this design did produce closed tones, the oval curve had a negative effect on the coloration of the instrument's sound, and the resulting performance effects were almost identical to the closed sounds of a horn - except that the latter were stronger.

These shortcomings became the reason that already in the first quarter of the 19th century, the half-moon pipe was completely out of use.

The result of the second attempt, which was also made at the end of the 18th century, was the so-called valve pipe. Although this type of instrument has received a certain distribution in military ensembles, this trumpet has almost never been used in symphonic music (the only exception was the opera "Robert the Devil" by J. Meyerbeer). As its name suggests, this trumpet had four or five valves and required the use of both hands during play; the newly introduced device, on the one hand, eliminated the peculiarities of sounding characteristic of a natural pipe, and on the other hand, caused dissonance in the extraction of sounds (which, in fact, led to its unpopularity).

The third variation on this theme was the trumpet with a stage, which became widespread, for example, in Great Britain and remained popular there until the second half of the 19th century. By design, it was similar to a trombone, with the difference that its wings did not move forward, but backward. This trumpet was characterized by a natural scale and four possible tunings: "fa", "mi", "e-flat" and "re".

The final end of the era of the natural pipe is associated with the invention of the valve mechanism, which is fundamentally similar to the modern one. However, the transition process was not instantaneous and proceeded differently in different countries of the world - for example, in France, for a rather long period of time, a cornet-a-piston with a piston mechanism was popular, and in Russia in the middle of the 19th century, the latter often were used in combination with valve pipes (in particular, such options are typical for Dargomyzhsky or Tchaikovsky). At the same time, many composers continued to actively use natural pipes even after the creation of new pipes, and only with time did the chromatic pipe of the modern type become widely used. During the transitional phase, the "old chromatic" pipe also spread - a natural pipe, but with a valve mechanism tuned to a tone, a semitone and a tone and a half, which made it possible to fill in the gaps between the main steps. The modern chromatic trumpet is, in essence, a shortened instrument, the appearance of which, to a certain extent, is due to the desire of composers for ever higher-sounding orchestral parts. Its device, which, in particular, is characterized by a predominantly conical scale and a cup-shaped mouthpiece of medium depth, caused the loss of fullness of sound characteristic of ancient pipes, but added clarity, sonority and some sharpness to the instrument.

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